

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEMOGRAPHIC FACTOR OF CONSUMERS ON PURCHASING DECISIONS

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Abstract

This work will explore the way demographic characteristics influence purchasing decisions on the example of buying technical products. Research for this work was conducted in the area of northeast of Bosnia and 192 examinees have filled out the questionnaire. After factor analysis were completed allegations of purchasing decisions are grouped into six factors, but two factors discarded from further analysis because the data collected for these factors were not reliable, as the results of values of Cronbach's Alpha indicators showed. Results of Multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) showed that gender, income level and employment status of examinees significantly influence the purchasing decisions among consumers. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) has further shown that females who have income less than 400 KM and have less than 25 years the most of the time are dedicating to purchasing decisions. The results of this analysis showed that the most satisfied with their purchasing decisions are male respondents who have incomes of 400 and 800KM, and at the same time are students and have less than 25 years.

Keywords : *Consumer behavior, Buying decisions, Demographic factors, Factor analysis, Multivariate analysis of variance*

JEL Classification: *C30, D10, J10*

1. Introduction

Nowadays more and more importance is being given to the study of the importance of consumer behavior in marketing. The environment in which companies are operating is increasingly changing and is very difficult to fight for the customer and market share [Khaniwale, 2014]. Each company must adapt to changes in the market in order to survive. Companies have to get to know their customers and their purchasing decisions.

Consumer behavior is a complex process that involves a variety of activities including: search, selection, purchase, use, evaluation of products and services in order to meet their needs and desires [Belch & Belch, 2004]. Number of factors divided into internal and external factors, and which can range from short-term to long-term emotional feelings, are affecting customer behavior [Hirschman, 1985]. Marketing experts have to understand the dynamics of internal factors that are influencing consumers' decisions. These factors vary from person to person, from situation to situation; therefore it is important to draw some generalizations of consumer behavior [Komal Prasad & Jha, 2014].

Main decisions that consumer returns are: what he buys (which products and services), how many purchases (amount), where (place of purchase), the time spent shopping and payment methods [Khaniwale, 2014]. This research is focused on the purchasing decision in the case of purchases of technical goods. The aim of this research is to find out how consumers behave and how they are deciding on buying technical equipment.

2. Theoretical Framework and Research Hypotheses

Consumer behavior involves the study of individuals, which method they are using to select products, and how they are using the products and services to fulfill their desires. Consumer behavior refers to all thoughts, feelings and actions that the individual has or had before or during the purchase of the product, service or idea. Main activity in the study of consumer behavior is the process of purchasing decision. The whole process of purchase decision making involves thinking about what to buy, what brand is good or appropriate, where to shop from and when, how much time to spend and at what intervals. Therefore, the end result of customer behavior is making a final decision on the product choice, brand choice, choice of retailers, time of purchase, purchase amount and frequency of purchase [Khaniwale, 2014].

Demographic, behavioral and psychographic factors help to understand consumers and their needs [Kotler & Armstrong, 2007]. In marketing surveys demographic factors such as age, number of household members, sex, income level and social class are used extensively, and are considered good indicators for the study of consumer behavior [Iqbal, Ghafour & Shahbaz, 2013]. Behavioral factors refer to way consumer behaves, how they accept certain products, why they accept it, etc. Psychographic factors are used for determining and evaluating the lifestyle of consumers, the ways they use their activities, interests and opinions [Tam & Tai, 1998] in this research attention will be on demographic characteristics of examinees.

When deciding on the purchase of various products consumers are making various efforts. The least effort is invested in the purchase of food products, deciding when purchasing these products is done automatically and without much thinking. When buying certain products like cars and some

technical equipment purchase is preceded by a long deciding and consideration of various options and ultimately make the final purchasing decision [Markovina, Kovacic & Radman, 2004]. Decisions that require strategic deciding are very specific and are characterized by: high involvement in decision-making, long-term resources acquiring and budget available for the purchase of other goods and services [Kos Koklič & Vida, 2009]. Sometimes the purchase of technical equipment requires major efforts in the decision-making process.

The level of decision making, which comes before the purchase is a very important factor in marketing research. Based on the obtained data about the level and complexity of decision making for individual product it is possible to conduct market segmentation and determine the targeted market where each company will operate. During market segmentation consumers can be divided according to the degree of involvement in the process to consumers of high, medium and low involvement. Using that is possible to create marketing messages to targeted consumers that will have the greatest impact on purchasing decision. Also, data on the involvement of consumers may be used to customize products. Previous researches have shown different behavior of consumers when purchasing depending on their involvement [Beatty & Smith, 1987].

The purchase decision-making process that consumer goes through includes following phases [Engel & Blackwell, 1978]:

1. recognition of the problem,
2. search for information,
3. estimating alternatives,
4. purchasing decision and
5. behavior after the purchase.

The first phase begins with the need or the recognition of the problem. This is followed by a search for alternatives that includes seeking information from various sources, internal and external environment, such as experience. The third phase involves consumer criteria in calculating benefits subjected to evaluating alternatives. When a decision is made, the consumer enters the fourth phase where the purchase of selected alternatives takes place. The final step involves post-purchase evaluation and consumer behavior after the purchase [SueLin, 2010].

Many factors influence the purchasing decision making. Demographic factors play an important role in the purchasing process. Income, age, occupation, and other demographic factors may influence decision-making [Anderson & Gaile-Sarkane, 2008]. Iqbal Ghafoor & Shahbaz, (2013) in their work showed that the following demographic factors influence the selection of shops in which to do the purchase: the level of education, occupation, income level, number of household members. Sharma & Kaur (2015) in their work proved that sex and marital status significantly affect the way of purchasing. Aloomaa & Lawan (2013) in their study showed that demographic factors: age, sex, marital status, occupation, education and income are the key variables that influence consumer behavior. Mazloumi, Efteghar, Ghalandari, Saifi, & Aghandeh, (2013) in their study demonstrated that gender, education, marital status, activity and age play an important role in the buying behavior of consumers. In accordance with these and other works following hypotheses are set in this work:

- H1 - There are significant differences in the purchasing decision-making with regard to gender

- H2 - There is a significant statistical difference in the purchasing decision making with regard to the amount of household income
- H3 - There is a significant statistical difference in the purchasing decision-making with regard to examinees level of education
- H4 - There is a significant statistical difference in the purchasing decision-making with regard to the examinees employment status
- H5 - There is a significant statistical difference in the buying decisions with regard to the examinees age
- H6 - There is a significant statistical difference in purchasing decisions with regard to the number of household members among the examinees

MANOVA analysis is going to be used for proving that hypothesis.

3. Research Methodology

Research for of this paper was conducted in northeastern Bosnia and Herzegovina in the period from January to May 2016. The aim of this study was to examine how respondents make their purchasing decisions when buying technical products. Convenience sample was used for data collection. For the realization of this research we have used online questionnaire placed on scientific portal 1ka.si. Link of research was forwarded to Facebook pages of largest portals in the region. 2,084 respondents have accessed online survey, and 192 respondents have completed the questionnaire, that is 9.21%.

The questionnaire consisted of two parts. The first part contained questions about demographic characteristics of respondents: sex, household income, education, employment status, age and the number of household members. The second part of the questionnaire contained 21 statements to which respondents should have answered ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" wherein Likert scale of 5 levels was used. Claims used in this group of questions are adapted from the following works: Beatty & Smith (1987), Jeyakumar & Paul Robert (2010), Bui, Krishen and Bates (2011) and Waheed, Mahasan & Sandhu (2014). Based on these works we have adjusted claims for consumer behavior when purchasing technical equipment. Statistical analysis of the data obtained in this study was performed using SPSS 20 software tool.

In this work following steps will be used:

1. Presentation of the demographic characteristics of respondents,
2. Grouping claims using factor analysis, and testing reliability of measurement scale of collected data,
3. Testing hypotheses using multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA)
4. Analysis of the influence of certain demographic characteristics of respondents in purchasing decisions via analysis of variance (ANOVA).

In order to examine results of the factor analysis we will use indicators of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin's (KMO) adequacy of the sample and Bartlett's test of sphericity. KMO value ranges in the closed interval from zero to one. If its value is less than 0.6 correlation matrix is not acceptable for factor analysis. In Bartlett's test it is preferred that the level of significance is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). [Puška, Maksimović & Fazlić, 2015]. During the implementation of factor analysis varimax

rotation of factors and Kaiser Normalization will be used. Reliability of the scale of collected data is tested using Cronbach's alpha coefficient whose results range from zero to one. If the value of this indicator is close to zero, then these data are unreliable, and if they are close to one then they are very reliable [Kozarević & Puška, 2015]. In order to accept a factor it is necessary that the value of Cronbach's alpha is higher than 0.7 [Tavakol & Dennick, 2011].

MANOVA is a statistical test for comparison of variances of arithmetic means of several groups, unlike the ANOVA analysis which hipper forms comparison of variances of arithmetic means of only one group or a factor. These analyzes are used to answer the question: Do the changes in the independent variable / s have significant effects on the change in the dependent variables [Grbić & Puška 2015]? In conducting of these analyzes we will examine how the demographic characteristics of respondents influence the purchasing decisions when buying technical products.

Testing of research hypotheses will be conducted at the level of inferential statistics of 0,05 ($p < 0,05$), which means that if the significance level is lower than the set level the null hypothesis as accepted, otherwise the alternative hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

4. Research Methodology

During the presentation of research results firstly we will present the basic characteristics of the respondents included in these results which are presented in Table 1.

Table – 1. Results of the demographic characteristics of the respondents

	Demographic variables	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	1. Male	118	61,5%
	2. Female	74	38,5%
Household income in KM	1. Less than 400	25	13,2%
	2. 401-800	57	30,0%
	3. 801-1200	44	23,2%
	4. More than 1201	64	33,7%
Level of education:	1. Primary education	6	3,1%
	2. Secondary Education	86	44,8%
	3. Higher education	32	16,7%
	4. University degree	68	35,4%
Employment status:	1. student	53	28,0%
	2. employed	99	52,4%
	3. unemployed	37	19,6%
Age:	1. 15-24	64	33,3%
	2. 25-40	103	53,6%
	3. 41-54	22	11,5%
	4. 55 and more	3	1,6%
Number of household members:	1. 1-2	40	21,5%
	2. 3-4	106	57,0%
	3. 5-6	43	18,3%
	4. 7 and more	6	3,2%

Source: Analysis results

Of the total 192 respondents, 61.5% of respondents are males, while 38.5% are females. Observing the household income of respondents, most of them have monthly household income of more than 1200 KM which is 33.7% of the respondents, next are respondents with a monthly household income between 401 and 800 KM which is 30.0%, followed by respondents that have a monthly

household income between 801 and 1200 KM with 23.3%, and finally last group of respondents with monthly household income of less than 400KM with 13.2%.

Educational background of respondents is that the most respondents are with a high school education with 44.8%, followed by respondents who have a university degree with 35.4%, then come respondents with higher education who are represented with 16.7%, while the least respondents have a lower level of education who are represented with 3.1%. Observing the employment status of respondents we can see that the most of respondents are employed with 52.1% followed by students with 27.9%, while there are the least respondents who are unemployed with 19.5%.

When it comes to the age of respondents the most respondents are aged between 25 and 40 years, with 53.6%, in second place are the respondents aged between 15 and 24 years with 33.3%, followed by respondents aged between 41 and 54 years with 11.5% while the least respondents have more than 55 years with 1.6%. When it comes to the number of the household members there are the most respondents with 3 or 4 members in a household with 57.0%, then come those who have one or two members in the household with 21.5% followed by respondents who have 5 or 6 members in a household with 18.3% while the least respondents have 7 or more members of the household with 3.2% respondents.

After demographic characteristics of respondents covered in this research have been presented, we will do grouping and analyzing collected data and determine whether they are acceptable for further analysis. Grouping statements that are represented in the second part of the questionnaire will be carried out by using factor analysis whose results are presented in Table 2. Apart from this analysis the table will contain calculated values of Cronbach's Alpha indicators that will be used to determine the reliability of measurement scale of the collected data.

The results of the factor analysis (Table 2) grouped claims in six factors. These factors explained 62.404% of the variance of the basic set which is a customary percentage that is present in social researches (Kurnoga Živadinović, 2004). Value of KMO indicator is higher than the required 0.6 (KMO = .800), while the value of Bartlett's test is lower than set level of significance ($p = .000$), which confirms the results of the factor analysis.

The first factor which is called "The role of the dealer in the purchase process," explains 27.458% of the variance. This factor has grouped five statements which are mostly related to the role of dealer in making purchasing decisions. Value of Cronbach alpha indicator is greater than 0.7 (.763) so that can confirm the reliability of the scale of collected data for this factor. Second factor that has been called "Satisfaction with purchasing decision", included four statements related to the satisfaction of respondents with the decision on the purchase of technical equipment and this factor explains 11.879% of the variance of the basic set. Results of Cronbach's alpha for this factor are greater than 0.7 (.745) which confirms that the collected data are reliable for further analysis. The third factor called "Searching for alternatives" included four statements that are related to the way of looking for alternatives by the respondents. This factor explains 7.194% of the variance of the basic set, and the value of Cronbach's alpha is very close to the set level of confidence (.699) so we can say that data that are grouped by this factor are reliable and acceptable for further analysis. The fourth factor called "Purchase decision" includes three claims that are related to the way in which respondents decide on the purchase of technical equipment. This factor explains 5.827% of the variance of the basic set and the resulting value of Cronbach's alpha indicators is higher than the set

level of reliability (.730) which proves that the data grouped by this factor are reliable for further analysis.

Fifth factor called "Previous experience" has grouped three claims related to previous experience with the shop or device that has a positive impact on the purchasing decision. This factor explains 5.258% of the variance of the basic set, and value of Cronbach's alpha for this factor is low (.646), so we can conclude that the data grouped by this factor are unreliable for further analysis. Low value of Cronbach's alfa could be caused by a small number of questions, weak correlation between the questions or heterogenic questions. Sixth factor called "Price and warranty" includes two items related to the impact of price and product warranty on the purchasing decision. This factor explains 4.787% of the variance of the basic set and the value of Cronbach's alpha is very low for this factor (.490) and, as with the previous factor it means that the data are unreliable and will not be used for further analysis.

Table – 2. Factor analysis of acceptability of collected data

	Factor					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
I accept the tips given to me by a salesman	.740					
When I cannot decide what to buy I ask the seller	.738					
I ask sellers for additional information	.722					
Seller plays a significant role in the purchase of technical products	.676					
I am looking for alternatives by visiting various shops	.559					
Factor 1. Role of the seller in purchasing process, explained variance = 27.458, Crobach's alpha = .763						
All the hard work that I put in the process of deciding on the purchase of technical products has paid off		.784				
When I buy a device, I feel very satisfied		.782				
After purchasing I do not feel guilty conscience that I could buy another product		.694				
I'm confident in my decision and am not changing it		.600				
Factor 2. Satisfaction with purchasing decision, explained variance = 11.879, Crobach's alpha = .745						
I ask my friends and acquaintances for help when buying technical products			.656			
I am looking for alternatives on the Internet			.619			
It takes me days to decide on the purchase of technical products			.564			
When I collect all possible alternatives I make the decision at home			.521			
Factor 3. Looking for alternatives, explained variance = 7.194, Crobach's alpha = .699						
I make decisions on the purchase of technical products at home				.774		
Usually I am not making decisions to purchase technical products on my own				.744		
I am buying a new technical product only when old one breaks or is outdated				.599		
Factor 4. Decision to purchase, explained variance = 5.827, Crobach's alpha = .730						
I am shopping only at certain stores where I have had positive experiences from past purchases					.756	
When buying technical products I buy trusted brands					.554	
When shopping I know exactly which product I will buy					.510	
Factor 5. Previous experience, explained variance = 5.258, Crobach's alpha = .646						
Price plays a key role in the purchase of technical products						.782
Warranty length has a very important role in						.622

purchasing of technical products

Factor 6. Price and warranty, explained variance = 4.787, Crobach's alpha = .490

KMO = .800, $\chi^2 = 1077.792$, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity = .000, explained variance = 62.404

Source: Analysis results

The results of the factor analysis have reduced the total number of claims from 21 to 16 that are grouped in four factors. In further analysis only the first four factors will be used because they have a reliable measurement scale, while last two factors are discarded from further analysis. Now we will use MANOVA analysis to examine hypotheses identified in this paper.

Table – 3. Testing the hypothesis using MANOVA analysis

Respondents' characteristics	F-test	Sig.	Status of hypothesis
Sex	5.172	.001	Accepted
Household income	1.973	.025	Accepted
Level of education	.985	.462	Discarded
Employment status	2.340	.018	Accepted
Age	1.049	.403	Discarded
Number of household members	1.127	.336	Discarded

Source: Analysis results

The results of MANOVA analysis (Table 3) show that three hypotheses are accepted, and three hypotheses are not accepted. This analysis showed that gender ($F = 5.172$, $p = .001$), household income ($F = 1.973$, $p = .025$) and employment status ($F = 2.340$, $p = .018$) play an important role in the purchasing decisions of the respondents. However, this analysis showed that the level of education ($F = .985$, $p = .462$), age ($F = 1.049$, $p = .403$) and the number of household members ($F = 1.127$, $p = .336$) do not play a significant role in purchasing decisions among the respondents included in this research, and that among these variables, there are no significant differences between their dimensions.

After testing hypothesis with MANOVA analysis we will use ANOVA analysis to examine the impact of certain factors within the individual characteristics of respondents to determine how and what factors respondents use when deciding on the purchase of technical equipment.

The results of the ANOVA analysis (Table 4) for the basic characteristic of respondents „Gender“ shows that there is a significant statistical difference in two factors: “The role of the dealer in the purchasing process” ($F = 7.466$, $p = .007$) and “Decision of purchase” ($F = 8.704$, $p = .004$), while in other two factors, there is no significant difference.

The ratio represents the arithmetic mean of the offered answers for certain dimensions of the basic characteristics of respondents in this case those are members of male and female gender. These relationships between factors are such that the female respondents have consulted more sellers, have looked for more alternatives, and got along with more statements when making decisions on the purchase of technical goods, while male respondents were more satisfied with their purchase decision.

When it comes to basic characteristic „household income“ obtained results showed that at two factors there is a significant statistical difference in the offered answers, and those factors are: "The role of the dealer in the purchasing process" ($F = 3.775$, $p = .012$) and the "Decision to purchase" ($F = 2.717$, $p = .046$), for other factors, there is no significant difference in the answers. The results

that show the ratio are such that the statements related to buying decision, are the most used by respondents with a monthly household income below 400 KM, and on second place are respondents with incomes higher than 1200 KM. Based on these results we cannot say that the household income plays a decisive role in the purchasing decision because the ones who have incomes between 400 and 1200 KM are the least satisfied with their purchasing decisions because they also use purchasing decisions the least.

Table – 4. Factors dependency on basic characteristics of the respondents

Respondents' characteristics	Factor	Variance	F-test	Sig.	Ratio
	The role of the dealer in the purchasing process	4.546	.466	.007	1<2
Sex	Satisfaction with purchasing decision	.946	.496	.223	2<1
	Looking for alternatives	.347	.531	.467	1<2
	Decision to purchase	7.500	.704	.004	1<2
	The role of the dealer in the purchasing process	2.278	.775	.012	3<4<2<1
Household income	Satisfaction with purchasing decision	.178	.283	.838	3<1<4<2
	Looking for alternatives	1.664	.601	.054	2<3<4<1
	Decision to purchase	2.389	.717	.046	2<3<4<1
Level of education	The role of the dealer in the purchasing process	.851	.358	.257	4<2<3<1
	Satisfaction with purchasing decision	.205	.320	.811	2<4<3<1
	Looking for alternatives	1.021	.581	.196	3<2<4<1
	Decision to purchase	1.459	.642	.181	4<3<2<1
Employment status	The role of the dealer in the purchasing process	.267	.430	.651	3<1<2
	Satisfaction with purchasing decision	2.277	.784	.025	3<2<1
	Looking for alternatives	.830	.315	.271	2<3<1
	Decision to purchase	3.454	.036	.019	2<3<1
Age	The role of the dealer in the purchasing process	1.052	.688	.171	4<2<3<1
	Satisfaction with purchasing decision	.638	.005	.392	3<2<1<4
	Looking for alternatives	.266	.405	.750	3<2<4<1
	Decision to purchase	2.199	.509	.060	2<3<1<4
Number of household members	The role of the dealer in the purchasing process	.416	.682	.564	3<4<2<1
	Satisfaction with purchasing decision	.791	.274	.285	4<1<2<3
	Looking for alternatives	1.254	.008	.115	4<2<3<1
	Decision to purchase	.781	.890	.447	4<2<1<3

Surce: Analysis results

The results obtained for the level of education of the respondents indicate that there is no significant statistical difference in the answers for any of the factors. What is characteristic about these results is that the purchasing decision is the most used by respondents who have lower levels of education, while the order in other dimensions ranges differently in comparison to other factors. So the least satisfied with the purchasing decision are the respondents with a University degree, respondents with higher education contact sellers the least and do not make decision to purchase at home, while respondents with higher education the least look for alternatives in the form of technical goods.

Using the basic characteristic „The employment status of the respondents“ obtained results showed that at two factors there is a significant statistical difference and those factors are: "Satisfaction with purchasing decision" ($F = 3.784$, $p = .025$) and the "Decision to purchase" ($F = 4.036$, $p = .019$), while the other factors, do not have significant difference in the answers. Results of the relationships show that the students are the most satisfied with purchasing decisions, are looking for alternatives the most, and make decisions at home, while employees contact sellers the most. Unemployed contact the sellers the least, and are the least satisfied with the buying decision, while employed respondents look for alternatives the least and do not make decisions to purchase at home.

The results for the primary characteristic „Respondents age“ shows that there is no significant difference in any of the factors. As for the relationship, respondents who have less than 25 years contact sellers the most and look for alternatives, while the most satisfied with the decision are the respondents who have more than 55 years. Results should be taken with some caution because there were only three respondents with more than 55 years. Respondents aged between 41 and 55 years are the least satisfied with the decision, and look for alternatives the least, while respondents aged between 25 and 40 years the least decisions to purchase make at home.

Observing results obtained for the basic characteristic „Number of household members“ can be seen that, there isn't significant difference for any of the factors. So it can be concluded that the number of household members does not particularly effect on purchasing decision. As for the relationship that the number of household members have on the purchasing decision, the respondents who have 1 or 2 members of the household use salesperson opinions the most, while respondents who have 5 or 6 members in the household are the most satisfied with purchasing decision. Respondents with seven or more members of the household use purchasing decisions the least.

5. Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to examine all the basic characteristics of respondents that significantly influence purchasing decisions. For the realization of this research we have used convenience sample and online questionnaire placed on scientific portal lka.si, and link of research was forwarded to Facebook pages of largest portals in northeastern Bosnia and Herzegovina. In this way, respondents used in this study are Internet users of these portals. In this way we have collected 192 completed questionnaires. The questionnaire consisted of two parts, first part contained questions about demographic characteristics of respondents: sex, household income, education, employment status, age and the number of household members. The second part of the questionnaire contained 21 statements to which respondents should have answered ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" wherein Likert scale of 5 levels was used.

Another objective of this paper was to determine how dimensions within the individual characteristics of the respondents use certain factors. Factor analysis was used to group claims related to purchasing decisions in factors. Conducted factor analysis grouped all claims in six factors. However, the analysis of reliability of collected data has confirmed that there are two factors with low value of the Cronbach's alpha and therefore these factors were not used in further analysis. Busied on that, the number of claims related to the purchasing decisions reduced from 21 of them to 16.

The results of the MANOVA analysis showed that for the following basic demographic characteristics there is a significant statistical difference which showed that gender, income level and the status of respondents play a significant role in purchasing decisions. Three hypotheses are proven in this research, while other three hypotheses are discarded, because it is proven that there is no significant statistical difference in following basic characteristics of the respondents: level of education, age and number of household members.

The implementation of the ANOVA analysis has found that female respondents consult more sellers, look for more alternatives, and decisions to purchase make at home. Male respondents are more satisfied with their purchase decision. Then it is proved that people with income less than 400 KM and people with low level of education spend most of their time on the purchasing decision. Results of this analysis showed that students are the most satisfied with purchasing decisions, are looking for most alternatives and make decisions to purchase at home, while employees contact sellers the most. During the observation of the age structure, it has been noticed that respondents who are younger than 25 years are contacting more sellers, and are looking for more alternatives. Number of household members can be concluded that it does not particularly effect on the purchasing decisions.

Based on these results it can be concluded that females who have income less than 400 KM and a lower level of education and at the same time have less than 25 years, spent most of the time in searching for alternatives. People who are male and have incomes higher than 800KM and are older than 55 years, use purchasing decisions the least. The most satisfied with their purchasing decisions are male respondents, who have incomes between 400 and 800km, and at the same time have a lower level of education, while being students and have less than 25 years.

However, this study was conducted has its shortcomings which should be resolved in future studies. The biggest drawback was the questionnaire because the claims about purchase decision-making were too similar so it was not possible to group the reliable data as shown in the results of Cronbach's Alpha. In future studies that will cover this topic it is necessary to determine the variables or factors that are affecting the purchasing decision and make questionnaire based on these factors. It is also necessary to include more subjects in research and cover a larger territory. Despite all these disadvantages, this paper represents one of the first papers that explored purchasing decisions in Bosnia and Herzegovina and that gave significant guidelines for future researches that will be conducted in this area.

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